

Ligand Bridged Polymeric Complexes of Some Bivalent Metal Ions with 1,4-Dithio -*p*-Urazine

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Manuscript received 30 May 1980, revised 11 November 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

The complexes of M(II) ions with 1,4-dithio-*p*-urazine (abbreviated as H₂dtpu) of compositions [M(dtpu)(H₂O)₂]*n*H₂O (*n*=2 for M=Ni(II) and 1.5 for Co(II)), M(dtpu)·2H₂O (M=Pb(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pd(II)) and Cd(dtpu)(NH₃)(H₂O) have been prepared and characterised. The spectral and magnetic properties of Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes are consistent with six coordinated distorted octahedral structure.

1, 4-Dithio-*p*-urazine contains six donor atoms and can exist in the following four tautomeric thiolthione forms¹:

Thus, depending upon the pH of the reaction medium H₂dtpu may coordinate as neutral, monobasic or dibasic acidic ligand.

In the present investigation, the preparation and characterisation of complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Pd(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) with the ligand have been made.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by the method of Sandstrom².

Preparation of metal complexes:

M(dtpu)·*n*H₂O {*n*=4 for M=Ni(II), 3.5 for Co(II) and 2 for Pb(II), Pd(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II)}:

The complexes were obtained by mixing 100 ml of 0.1 molar methanolic solution of hydrated metal acetates (chlorides in case of palladium) with 0.012 mole of the ligand dissolved in 100 ml of methanolic solution of sodium acetate (3%). The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for about 20 minutes. The

products were filtered, washed with dilute methanolic solution of sodium acetate followed by excess of water, methanol and ether, and finally dried in a desiccator over CaCl₂.

Cd(dtpu)(NH₃)(H₂O):

An ammoniacal solution of cadmium chloride (0.01 mole in 100 ml of 1:2 aqueous ammonia) was treated with aqueous ammoniacal solution of the ligand in 1:1 molar ratio. The title complex was obtained as a white crystalline product. The precipitate was filtered, washed with dilute ammonia, alcohol and ether, and dried in a vacuum desiccator over KOH.

Almost all the complexes of 1,4-dithio-*p*-urazine were obtained in 90-98% yield. In a few cases the precipitation was almost quantitative. The complexes were obtained in sufficiently pure state. These complexes are almost insoluble in water and organic solvents, therefore these were not crystallised and their molecular weight could not be determined.

TABLE I

Complex	Colour	(% M)		(% N)	
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Ni(dtpu)·4H ₂ O	Dark brown	21.01	21.21	20.67	20.23
Co(dtpu)·3.5H ₂ O	Dark brown	21.90	21.99	20.87	20.90
Pd(dtpu)·2H ₂ O	Dark red	36.14	36.95	18.90	19.39
Zn(dtpu)·2H ₂ O	White	26.56	26.43	22.27	22.64
Cd(dtpu)·2H ₂ O	White	38.22	38.18	19.39	19.02
Pb(dtpu)·2H ₂ O	Light yellow	53.51	53.23	14.35	14.38
Cd(dtpu)(NH ₃)(H ₂ O)	White	38.28	38.31	23.57	23.85

TABLE 2

Complex	μ_{eff} at 26° (BM)	Band's position (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments
Co(dtpu).3.5H ₂ O	3.76	17,860 m	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ A _{2g} (F)
		21,280 sh	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)
		25,640 m	C-T
Ni(dtpu).4H ₂ O	3.05	10,530 w	³ B _{1g} → ³ E _g ^a
		13,510 m	³ B _{1g} → ³ B _{2g}
		14,840 sh	³ B _{1g} → ³ A _{2g}
		18,250 w	³ B _{1g} → ³ E _g ^b

and its metal complexes were recorded in KBr disc in the range 4000-200 cm⁻¹ (Table 3) on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, model 577.

Results and Discussion

The ligand is almost insoluble in neutral organic solvents like ethanol, methanol, benzene etc. but dissolves in basic medium like pyridine, methanolic sodium acetate solution etc. In alkaline medium, the ligand readily coordinates with transition metal ions as well as with Pb²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ forming insoluble complexes (shown in Table 1). Due to poor solubility of the ligand in water and in neutral organic solvents, the complexes of the ligand in its neutral or monobasic acidic form could not be prepared.

TABLE 3—IR BANDS IN cm⁻¹

H ₂ dtpu	M (dtpu) . nH ₂ O		Assignments
	M = Zn (II), Cd (II) & Pb (II)	M = Pd (I), Co (II) & Ni (II)	
	3450 - 3350 br	3425 - 3375 br	γ(H ₂ O)
3162 mbr 3058 m 2819 m	3260 - 3200 m	3350 - 3200 w	γ(N-H)
	1610 ± 5 w	1610 ± 5 sh	δ(H ₂ O)
1540 s 1520 sh 1480 sbr	1580 ± 15 ssp	1555 - 1520 sbr	Thioamide Band I
1380 vs	1380 ± 2 s	1425 - 1300 wbr	Thioamide Band II
1203 vsbr	1225 ± 5 vs	1220 ± 2 m	γ(C-N) +
	1178 ± 5 s	1182 ± 5 w	γ(N-N) vibrations
1120 sh	1105 ± 5 m		
1040 m	1060 ± 10 w 955 ± 10 w 890 ± 5 m	1060 ± 10 w 955 ± 10 wbr	Thioamide Band III
	840 - 800 wbr	830 ± 5 wbr	Out of plane bending of coordinated water
760 sh	770 w	765 ± 5 w	τ(N-H)
707 vsbr	685 ± 5 w	685 ± 10 w	Thioamide Band IV
	580 ± 5 w	570 ± 10 w	δ(H ₂ O)
500-480 sbr	520 ± 5 sbr	530 ± 5 sbr	
298 s			

m=medium ; w=weak ; s=strong ; br=broad ; v=very and sh=shoulder.

The colour and elemental analyses of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. Uv and visible reflectance spectra and magnetic susceptibilities were determined (Table 2) as reported earlier⁸. Ir spectra of the ligand

The complexes M(dtpu). nH₂O {M=Co(II), Ni(II) and Pd(II)} are obtained as a dark brown or a dark red insoluble precipitate. The Zn(II), Pb(II) and Cd(II) complexes are initially obtained as a white or yellow

precipitate but they gradually turn reddish brown probably due to superficial oxidation of the coordinated ligand molecule to 1,4-dithiotetrazine².

The complexes, in general, are insoluble in water and common organic solvents such as ethanol, methanol, dioxane etc indicating their polymeric nature. The complexes are quite stable below 70-80°. The hydrated nickel(II) complex, Ni(dtpu).4H₂O and cobalt(II) complex, Co(dtpu).3.5H₂O, however, lose 2 and 1.5 water molecules respectively between 90° and 120°. The complex, M(dtpu).2H₂O {M=Cd(II), Zn(II) and Pb(II)}, above 90-100°, gradually lose water molecules but anhydrous complexes could not be obtained even at 150-160°.

From thermal loss, it is inferred that at least two water molecules are coordinated to cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes and the remaining are either lattice water or weakly bonded to metal ion.

Magnetic susceptibility :

The zinc(II), cadmium(II), lead(II) and palladium(II) complexes are diamagnetic while those of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) are paramagnetic. The nickel(II) complex shows magnetic moment value similar to six coordinated nickel(II) complexes^{4,5} (Table 2). The complex Co(dtpu).3.5H₂O shows anomalous magnetic susceptibility e.g., its μ_{eff} value intermediates between those of spin free and spin paired octahedral cobalt(II) complexes^{6,7}. The existence of spin state equilibrium^{6,7} could not be confirmed due to lack of facilities.

Uv and visible spectra :

Nickel(II) complex, Ni(dtpu).4H₂O, displays four weak bands or shoulders in the region 25000 - 10000 cm⁻¹. The reflectance bands are similar to ligand field transitions in distorted octahedral complexes^{8,9} (Table 2). The reflectance spectrum of Co(dtpu).3.5H₂O displays a medium intensity band at 17860 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder near 21280 cm⁻¹, assignable¹⁰ to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴A_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions. The former is generally not observed but seems to have gained intensity due to a large tetragonal distortion¹¹. A medium intensity band at 25640 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to charge transfer transition.

Ir spectra :

The ir spectra of H₂dtpu and its metal complexes have been assigned (Table 3) by comparing with the ir spectra of similar compounds¹²⁻¹⁶.

Ir spectrum of H₂dtpu (KBr disc) displays broad and medium intensity bands at 3162, 3058 and 2819 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν (N-H) vibrations of the ligand. The broadening of the N-H stretching bands and their red shifting are most likely due to inter or intra molecular hydrogen bonding.

The absence of ir bands between 2600 - 2200 cm⁻¹ [expected for ν (S-H) vibrations] in the spectrum of the

ligand as well as its metal complexes rules out the possibility of thiol form of the ligand in solid state.

The metal complexes of dithio-*p*-urazine display relatively a sharp and medium intensity (N-H) band in the range 3200 - 3350 cm⁻¹ indicative of absence of bonding of NH to the metal ion. Thus the bonding of the ligand is taking place through the deprotonated thioamide group in the complexes. The hydrated complexes display very broad and medium intensity band at 3350 - 3450 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν (O-H) vibration of water molecule. In some complexes, the ν (N-H) vibration is overlapping with ν (H₂O) vibration of coordinated or lattice water molecules. In the ir spectra of Cd(dtpu)(NH₃)(H₂O), broad and strong bands at 3420, 3340 and 3150 cm⁻¹ are attributable to ν (NH) and ν (H₂O) vibrations of coordinated ammonia and water molecule.

The characteristic infrared vibrations of the thioamide group have been observed^{12,13}. The ligand displays strong and broad bands at 1540 and 1480 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder at 1520 cm⁻¹ assigned to thioamide band I. In the metal complexes, M(dtpu).2H₂O [M = Cd(II), Zn(II) or Pb(II)] and Cd(dtpu)(NH₃)(H₂O), possessing tetrahedral structure, the thioamide band I appears as a strong and sharp band at 1580 ± 15 cm⁻¹. In case of other aquo complexes, possessing chemical composition M(dtpu).nH₂O {M = Pd(II), Co(II) and Ni(II); n = 2, 3.5 and 4 respectively}, the thioamide band I appears as a very broad and strong band at 1555 - 1520 cm⁻¹. The broadness of thioamide band I and its occurrence at relatively lower wave number in complexes of the type M(dtpu).nH₂O {M = Pd(II), Co(II) and Ni(II)} than those of M(dtpu)(H₂O)₂ {M = Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II)} suggest that the thioamide group is probably bonded to metal ion in the former while through sulphur atom only in the latter type of complexes.

A strong band at 1380 cm⁻¹ in the ligand is assignable to thioamide band II. In complexes of the type M(dtpu)(H₂O)₂ {M = Zn(II), Cd(II) or Pb(II)} the band is not affected appreciably, while in complexes, M(dtpu)(H₂O)_n {M = Co(II), Ni(II) and Pd(II)} the band becomes broad and weak indicating that the mode of bonding of the ligand molecule in the latter series of complexes is different.

The ligand exhibits a very strong and broad band at 1203 cm⁻¹. This band is assigned to the combination of ν (N-N) + ν (C-N) vibrations. The band splits up into two strong bands irrespective of the nature of the complexes. The splitted bands are strong and sharp in the complexes M(dtpu)(H₂O)₂ {M = Zn(II), Pb(II) and Cd(II)} while medium and broad in other complexes.

The ligand exhibits a band of medium intensity at 1040 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to thioamide band III [major ν (C-N) + minor ν (C=S)]. The band splits up into two weak bands in its complexes. The first band is located at 1060 ± 10 cm⁻¹ while the second at

$955 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Owing to the bonding of the metal ions with thiol sulphur [since it reduces the bond order of (C=S) and increases the bond order of C-N group in $\begin{matrix} -N \\ | \\ -C-S-M \\ | \\ -NH \end{matrix}$ than that of $\begin{matrix} -NH \\ | \\ C=S \\ | \\ -NH \end{matrix}$], the splitting of thioamide band III is quite reasonable.

The thioamide band IV of the ligand, which is mainly due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ band, is observed as a strong and very broad band at 707 cm^{-1} . In its metal complexes the band appears at $685 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with reduced intensity.

All aquo complexes display a broad and weak band between $800 - 840 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to coordinated water molecule^{8,17}. The shoulder near $1610 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the aquo complexes also supports the presence of coordinated or lattice water in these complexes. The complexes, $\text{M}(\text{dtpu})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ {M=Zn(II), Pb(II) and Cd(II)}, display some new bands at $1105 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $890 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be attributed to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ and (N-H) wagging vibration of coordinated H_2dtpu molecule. In free ligand these bands are probably enveloped by strong and broad ligand absorptions around 1040 cm^{-1} . In case of Co(II), Ni(II) and Pd(II) complexes, these bands are very weak. Thus, from the ir spectra of $\text{M}(\text{dtpu})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ [M=Zn(II), Cd(II) or Pb(II)], the ligand appears to be bonded through sulphur atom only in these complexes.

In far infrared region the ligand displays strong and broad bands at $480 - 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 298 cm^{-1} . The former is shifted to higher frequency by $20 - 40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ while the latter disappears in its metal complexes. The ir spectra of the complexes do not display distinct M-N or M-S vibrations.

Thus from the ir spectra, the following probable structures can be suggested for H_2dtpu complexes.

Structure - A

[X=NH₃ in case of Cd(dtpu)(H₂O)(NH₃) and H₂O in case of Zn(dtpu).2H₂O, Cd(dtpu).2H₂O and Pb(dtpu).2H₂O].

Structure - B

[X=H₂O when M=Ni(II) and Co(II) and X=nil when M=Pd(II)].

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